

Adopting laughter therapy to get dosage of happy hormones to remove stress caused by being in slight pain, being depressed, being unhappy anxious or sad. Saying positive affirmations aloud changes body cell energy

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Abstract:

Statement of the Problem: There is a lack of awareness about what happy hormones are, how to use positive words to feel energetic and what can be done to get happy hormones. People tend to feel unhappy for multiple reasons and neuropathic pain adds on Stress levels of not only the patient but the caregivers as well. Being in pain leads to feeling depressed and anxious in some cases.

Methodology & Theoretical Orientation: Review of Books and Research shows that getting a dosage of happy hormones will not only ease slight pain of the patient but feeling happy will also have a positive impact on the recovery of the patient. Adopting Laughter therapy and getting hormones which makes one feel good will help many to recover from Neuropathic pain /Long term sadness caused by having grief, Anger or Resentment, Depression & Anxiety.

Findings: One needs to work on his/her energies using Laughter Therapy which is a positive approach for not having Depression & Anxiety caused by Neuropathic pain. The therapy can be used as a Holistic way to recovery.

Conclusion & Significance: The Laughter therapy which includes ways to get the dosage of happy hormones promotes overcoming Depression & Anxiety caused by Neuropathic pain, is a fun way to manage pain. Repeated sessions to be conducted to remind patients that life while having pain or during the recovery should go beyond just seeking medical and counselling help and also include rebuilding Spiritual, Physical, Emotional, Relational and Mental health. The model has been put together from for testing in many settings including hospitals, elderly homes and senior citizen centres. This is not a research book or paper. It is just an effort to demystify the help available for Depression & Anxiety caused by pain. It is an attempt to motivate and encourage people to seek help and take a simple approach to remember and work on all aspects of their recovery.

Biography:

MS. SUCHI is an experienced International Pre School Principal/Manager who picked up Laughter exercises from many coaches around the world. She then designed 'Laughter Therapy' which is being used in many places such as hospitals and Senior Activity Centres. She provides individual and group therapy in educational and home settings.

A former Manager / Trainer is now engages in building social awareness about Holistic approach for recovery. Be it Depression, Anxiety caused by physical or emotional pain, Death in the family and the harm the unhappiness brings to people, families and communities. Her aim is to encourage people to seek help early and get on the path to recovery. Her works has been featured in local press, TV and Radio and has been an invited speaker at various community clubs and educational Institutions. She has also been awarded by MINDS and various community clubs in recognition of her social work.

Unlocking the human potential and abundance through the power of brain; the right mind-set

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Abstract:

Statement of Problem: In this Volatile, Uncertain, Complex and Ambiguous (VUCA) world where things are not static, we are often faced with situations in life which requires us to move from known to unknown. This transition requires alignment of the mind-set, nurturing our brain in the right direction. It is found that many people are stuck in this transition process leading to unhappiness, pain and stress thus limiting the human potential and abundance.

Methodology and Theoretical Orientation : Review of books and Research shows that activating; nurturing the brain, the right mind set can help people overcome their limiting thought patterns and beliefs. Deep understanding of brain can result in building powerful habits, relationships, taking effective decisions and being effective in every role one executes. Most important it results in building resilience: the Adversity Quotient.

Findings: The paradigm shift in this disruptive world needs to be from mere Intelligent quotient to Emotional Quotient to understanding and leveraging the Consciousness Quotient; the Self-awareness quotient. To be happy which the common goal of most of us is we need to activate our inner compass through the power of brain by cultivating the right mind-set. We need to trim off non serving beliefs and unlock the human potential and abundance

Conclusion and significance: Transformation of our mind-set, tuning in to activate the power of our growth oriented brain can transform our lives. The theme and the model of tuning into Self-awareness quotient has resulted in unlocking the potential and abundance. There is a strong correlation between right mind-set and abundance in very space of life.

Model

Illustration 1

Illustration 2

Biography:

Puja has over a decade of rich and accomplished experience in Human Resources in the varied sectors globally. She has been recognised, by her clients for her out of box thinking & Result based approach. She was the first Professional in her family and the youngest member in senior leadership role for a leading global manufacturing organisation. She has driven successfully many initiatives for the entrepreneurs, women, millennial and young leaders. She is an internationally certified Life and Executive coach. She feels humbled on being mentored by John Matttone (ex-coach of Steve Jobs) in the leadership space. She has been recognised for her leadership roles and recently was conferred as 51 influential women and for her work in millennial space she is on bold mission on creating communities of courageous, authentic leaders who are inspiring, have right mind set and can ignite hope and create more leaders around